

Chhau Performance of Manbhum: A Folk Study of Hindu Traditions and Myths

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Abstract

This paper examines the role of Hindu traditions and myths in the *Chhau Dance of Manbhum*, exploring how the dance is structured around traditional and mythological references. The *Chhau Dance* form originates in the *Chhotanagpur* Plateau of Eastern India. Having crossed local boundaries, this dance form has acquired worldwide recognition. The study employs an ethnographic approach, drawing on theories of Folklore, Myth-Ritual, Structuralism in Myth, and Rasa. The findings demonstrate the significant use of rituals and myths as narrative source material, performance framework, and a means of enacting Hindu religious practice. In conclusion, Chhau Dance is an ancient cultural tradition that has served as a bearer of classical Indian culture across the ages.

Keywords

Purulia Chhau; Folk Performances; Hindu Mythology; Myth-Ritual Tradition; Masked Dance Performance

Introduction

Background

The *Chhau Dance of Manbhum*, also known as *Purulia Chhau*, is a folk tradition deeply saturated with Hindu customs and mythology. It is one of three distinct types of Chhau Dance, alongside *Seraikela* and *Mayurbhanj Chhau*. This dance form is performed as a kind of dance drama, incorporating Hindu beliefs and patterns of worship. It is often performed to please Lord Shiva, the presiding deity. Performances are organised on the occasions of Puja and various Hindu festivals, and propagate the idea of the victory of good over evil. Every performance begins with the dance of *Ganesha*, known as '*Ganesh Vandana*'.

The structure of the episode known as '*Pala*' is based on Hindu myth. Hindu gods and goddesses, such as *Ganesha*, *Kartika*, *Shiva*, *Krishna*, *Parshuram*, *Durga*, and *Mahamaya*, are some essential characters. The devil powers in the form of 'Asur' remain there in the story. The stories from Ramayan, Mahabharata and Puran take the form of '*Pala*' in this dance form.

Objectives

The root of a research work is its objectives. In the aspects of Hindu rituals, myth and gender liminality in the *Chhau Dance of Manbhum*, the main objectives of this study are to investigate and critically analyse -

- The elements of Hindu culture and myth in this culture
- The projection of a mythical character in folk dance
- The secret behind the accurate performance of a male *Chhau* artist as a female and his social acceptance and lifestyle in details

Significance of the Study

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The practice of Hindu culture and mythology by Hindus from the upper caste in popular places is highlighted, but its practice in rural India through folk culture has not received much importance. A highly rich culture like *Chhau Dance*, filled with a religious vibe remain underrated as a religious performance.

The quality of *Chhau Dance* as an easy medium of demonstrating difficult religious ethics and morals is not recognised. The modern society people, accustomed to smartphones and a luxurious lifestyle, remain detached from this rich culture invented by their ancestors.

Chhau Dance of Manbhum is rich with the ethics of Hinduism. It is one of the best media to reach the common folks with religious morals. This indigenous culture has the power to create a society well known for Hindu rituals and myths.

Methodology

Theories like Folklore, Myth-Ritual, Structuralism in Myth, and Rasa theory are used in this study. Folklore theory by Alan Dundes examines oral traditions, rituals and cultural projection of the society. In *Chhau Dance*, local narratives, ritual practices, and Song (*Jhumair*) are essential parts. The Myth-Ritual theory of James George Frazer and Bronislaw Malinowski is used here to explain the connection of *Chaitra Parav*, the projection of the battle between good vs evil in Puranas, *Ramayana*, *Mahabharata*, such as *Mahishasura vs Durga*, *Krishna vs Kansa* and other *Asuras*, *Ram vs Ravana*, the battle of *Kurukshetra*, etc. In the context of Structuralism in Myth, Claude Levi-Strauss argued for the binary oppositions. In *Chhau Dance*, good vs evil, divine vs demonic and order vs chaos are very frequent in the episodes. *Natyashastra* by Bharat Muni deals with eight *Rasas*. In *Chhau Dance* *Veer Rasa* (Heroic), *Raudra Rasa* (Anger), *Karuna Rasa* (Pathetic), *Shringara Rasa* (Love), *Adbhuta Rasa* (Wonder), *Bibhatsa Rasa* (Odious), everything has a role to describe the situations. *Raudra*, *Veer*, *Shringara*, and *Karuna Rasa* are used very often. The steps and rhythm reflect the heroism. Along with these case studies, literature review, analysis of the performances are used as tools for this study.

Review of Literature/Scholarship

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In the field of *Chhau Dance of Purulia*, the book *ManbhunyaChhau* (2021), edited by Kshirod Chandra Mahato and Shibshankar Sing, is the most remarkable book. This book has a collection of articles and essays by Kshirod Chandra Mahato, Shibshankar Sing, Sristidhar Mahato, and Md. Kshurshid Alam, Ramanath Das, Malay Choudhuri, Kiriti Mahato and Subrata Mukhopadhyay. It contains interviews of notable Ustad as well as artists like Dhananjay Mahato, Anil Sutradhar, Anil Mahato, Hem Mahato, Nepal Mahato and Mousumi Choudhuri. The book is enriched with the biography of thirty-seven popular *Chhau* artists who are promoted to the position of Ustad, the Master. These thirty-seven Ustad include Padmashree Gambhir Sing Mura, Padmashree Nepal Mahato, Lal Mahato, Juru Kumar, Madhu Ray (Bhat) Banu Thakur, Rasu Hari, Dhenukdhari Sing, Kalebar Kumar, Buka Sing, Gendhu Tanti, Gopal Shunri, Jagru Mahato, Bhuti Sing, Adalat Mahato, Bhagaban Das Kumar, Binadhar Kumar, Bikal Rajak, Gabra Hari, Kuyla Muchi, Satish Mahato, Giasuddin Ansary and many more. Sufficient details of a few teams like Nalkupi, Khatjuri, Shulungjhuri, Balarampur Royal *Chhau* are given in the book. The entire book mainly discusses the history, origin, evolution, gradual development, crisis, use of masque, music, rhythm, melody, dance pattern and drama pattern of Puruliya *Chhau*.

A research work titled *Reconfiguring Performative Traditions: A Mnemocultural Inquiry into the Chhau Dance of Purulia* by Shaktipada Kumar discusses in detail the various instruments and relations of Puruliya *Chhau*. The book *Chhau Dance of Purulia* by Ashutosh Bhattacharya is reviewed to seek some information about this content. Another book, *Seemanto Banglar Lokjan* by Dr Sudhir Kumar Karan, covers a vital portion on the background of the dance form.

More Sources

Virtual sources like articles, online documents, youtube video, etc. are used as important sources. Watching the live performances by the author on the stages of rural *Manbhum* is a primary source for this study.

Results and Discussion

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Chhau Dance: Origin, Types, Aspects, Social Effects as Folk Culture

The study found that this chapter is about the folk culture named *Chhau Dance* with its three types, namely Seraikella, Mayurvanj and Puruliya *Chhau*. This is a semi-classical dance form. This study mainly deals with the Puruliya or Manbhunya *Chhau*, which is more vigorous. Purulia *Chhau Dance*, a type of *Chhau Dance*, is centred in the district of Purulia, West Bengal. The popular pronunciation is 'Chha'; i.e. the number six. This dance form is an amalgamation of six patterns, steps, Rasa, dances and the use of six body organs. Six patterns often comprise *Chail* (stepping), *Chalan* (appearance), *Rangbaji* (vigorous activity), *Ghura* (Rounding), *Ulta* (falling down) and *Digbaji* (flipping). Purulia *Chhau Dance* is defined in its use of colourful masks and costumes, vigorous action, martial arts, powerful acrobat and risky physical strength.

The geographical location of *Manbhum* is in a rough weather. People have to go through a lot of physical hardship in their lives. This builds their physical strength and potential. For these reasons, the people of this area have the capacity to fulfil the kinetic requirements of *Chhau Dance* through robust activities. The people of this area are less ambitious in terms of financial establishment. Their livelihood mainly depends on agriculture and a little bit of miscellaneous work. They have enough time to practice their culture. This gives relaxation through entertainment to overcome the hardships of life.

Outline the structure of performance

The backdrop of this dance form is constructed upon the Hindu rituals and mythical characters. The narrative style and melodramatic performance match the ancient vibes of Hinduism. In a usual performance at night, a team performs three episodes: 1. *Vandana*, 2. *Asur Badh Pala*, 3. *Kirat Taal*.

Vandana: This *Pala* is actually *Ganesh Vandana* involving the characters of *Kartik*, *Shiva*, *Durga*, *Saraswati*, *Laxmi*, *Nandi*, *Vringi*, *Parshuram*, sometimes *Mahisasur* and others. *Parshuramer Gurudakshina*, *Ganesher Mundchhedan O Gajamunda Dharan*, and *Mahisasur Badh* are examples of *Vandana Pala*.

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Asur Badh Pala: This *Pala* generally includes Mel Nach of *Devta*, *Asur*, entry of *Bramha* as wish giver, entry of *Bishnu or Krishna* as saviour and lastly the vigorous fight with excellent acrobat performance. One or two *Asur* (demon) play the main role in this *Pala*. A long performance of *Asur Nach* takes place with lots of robust steps, volts, and somersaults. Some famous names in the role of *Asur* are Sasadhhar Kalindi, Adalat mahato, Trilocahan Karmakar, Bijay Krishna Kumar, Karna Karmakar, Sudarshan Sing, Prasenjit Sing, and Deepak Sing. A long performance or It involves long performance of *Krishna Dance*, beautifully projecting the mixing of *Veer* and *Shringara Rasa* through the performance. This dance is one of the most aesthetic. This performance requires a very skilled artist. Very often, the main artist plays this role. Famous Krishna dancers of Purulia Chhau are Banshidhar Mahato, Adalat Mahato, Binadhhar Kumar, Yudhistir Mahato, Samiran Karmakar, Gouranga Sing Sardar, Pradyugna Kumar Mahato and many more.

Kirat Taal: This *Pala* is about three characters: *Kirat*, *Kirateen* and *Arjun*. The *Pala* is based on the *Jhumair* song most of the time. The content of the songs appeals to the daily life of the people of the area. Nowadays, comedy *Pala* has taken the place of *Kirat Taal*. Dhunda (Dhananjay) Mahato is the most famous name in the role of *Kirat*.

Rhythm and music

A particular rhythm is intended for a particular character according to the situation. There are slight differences in rhythm for a character in different teams or different areas. The rhythm and bits are different in *Baghmundi*, *Kotshila* and *Barabazar Gharanas* (Cultural location). A team modifies the rhythm according to the requirements. *Shiv Bajna* (bit) is also different in *Barabazar* and *Kotshila*. But very often the rhythms of a few *Bajnas* like *Kartik*, *Krishna*, *Durga*, *Asur*, and *Muni* is same. Music is generated through instruments like *Dhol*, *Dhamsha*, *Tasa*, *Sanai*, *Casio*, etc.

Example:**Music and Rhythm of *Kartik Nach*:**

Song: *Kartikereo Biro Taape, Swarga Marta Patal Kanpe,*

Mata Jaro Parboti, Pita Panchanan Go Shuno Shuno sabhajana,

Amra Kori Nibedon Go Shuno Shuno Savajano.

(For the heroic fire of *Kartika*, Heaven, Earth and Underworld is shaking,

Whose mother is *Parvati*, father *Pancahnan*, listen, listen everyone,

We request everyone, listen, listen everyone.)

Rhythm and Bits:

Katan/ Taal: *Ur Tak Tak Tak Tak Ta Khete tak ta,*

Gidin-ti Genjhen Gejagin, Ur Ta Tere Khete Ta,

Gidin-ti Genjhen Gejagin, Ur Ta Tere Khete Ta,

Jhan Gejagin, Jhan Gejagin, Gindi Tak Tak Tak,

Gidin-ti Genjhen Gejagin, Gidin-ti Genjhen Gen,

Tiyak Tiyak Gindin, Tiyak Tiyak Gindin, Tiyak Tiyak Gindin.

Chail (stepping): *Ur Ta Tere Khete Ta* (many times)

The Chhau Dance is mainly male-dominated, but recently, females have also taken part in this culture. But in the male team, only male dancers participate, and in the female team, only female dancers participate. Even the female roles in a male team are also played by males with female attire and appearance. The roles of Durga, Kali, Rakshasi, and Nartaki are played by males with extraordinary perfection. In the female team, the roles of male characters like Ganesha, Kartika, Shiva, Asur, Krishna, and Raja are played by female artists.

Famous Chhau Dancers are Gambhir Sing Mura, Juru Kumar, Lal mahato, Rasu Hanri, Gopal Shunri, Hem Mahato, Adalat Mahato, Banshi Mahato, Anil Mahato, Tulsi, Samiran Karmakar, Nripen Sahis, Sasadhar Kalindi, Baghambar Sing Mura, Prabhudas Kumar, Bina Kumar, Bhagaban Das Kumar, Sanjay Orang, Gouranga Sing Sardar and many more. Names of famous Nartaki dancers are Rasbihari Kumar, Bikash Mahato, Uttam Mahato, Rabin Ray, Mangal Mahato, Manoj Kalindi, Biras Karmakar, Balai and many more. Famous Dhol players are Biren Kalindi, Jagannath Kalindi, Anil Mahato, Bhishma Mahato, Ramsaran Kalindi, Hem Mahato, Debilal Karmakar, Rampada Sing, Shambhu Kalindi, and Suman Badyakar. Famous Jhumair singers are Gobindalal Mahato, Laxmikanta Majhi, Parameshwar Kumar, Mahammad Ansari, Gour Mahato, Prahlad Sing Babu and many more.

It is very much essential to highlight the existence of highly Hindu teachings in an indigenous dance form like Chhau. It can be established as one the popular medium of teaching in the form of entertainment. Folk culture in its region can be the best medium to propagate a complicated idea.

After going through the different works related to Chhau Dance, it can be said that the excellent projection of the mythical characters by a crew of so-called illiterate people is neglected. It is proper evidence of practicing morals and spirituality through the medium of arts and culture. The culture is so well known to the common folk that most of the people have the knowledge about the rhythms, songs, steps and stories. These things properly match the outcome of a culture to mobilise the society.

Conclusions

The study has found very important observations regarding the impact and relation of Chhau Dance with society, spirituality and religion. People are very much habituated to the culture. The performances take place very often, sometimes in the evening, sometimes at night. Artists are generally from poor families with a dark economic future. But they nourish the culture with their own willpower. Not only are the artists, but the audience is also very

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much dedicated. There is enough gathering in every performance. They appreciate the artists. The family members of the artists are also very much supportive. They provide enough backup and inspiration to the artists. Artists are made from very childhood as they have firsthand experience of the culture.

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